

Short communication

FIRST RECORD OF *APLOCNEMUS (DIPLAMBE) ABIETUM* KIESENWETTER, 1859 (COLEOPTERA: RHADALIDAE) FROM BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

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The *Aplocnemus* subgenus *Diplambe* Schilsky, 1894 is distinctly delineated by its characteristic doubled elytral edge in the basal half of the elytral length and by the special morphology of its tegmen (Peacock, 1987; Majer, 1987; Liberti, 2019). Majer (1987) proposed elevating the subgenera of *Aplocnemus* Stephens, 1830 to full generic rank; however, this has not been done yet, despite most modern researchers agreeing with Majer's opinion on rhadalid beetles.

Diplambe species are distributed around the Mediterranean Basin in the Iberian Peninsula, Maghreb, Sicily, Sardinia, the Balkans, Anatolia, Cyprus, and the Levant. The complexity of their taxonomy is compounded by their uniformity and the scarcity of new specimens for some regions. However, the antennal structure, color, and median lobe shape are considered sufficient for identification (Liberti, 2021). So far, the faunas of the Iberian and Balkan peninsulas and the islands Sicily, Sardinia, and Cyprus have undergone revision (Liberti, 1995, 2007, 2019, 2021; Constantin, 2005), and those of Turkey and the Near East are under discussion (Liberti, 2021).

New country record:

***Aplocnemus (Diplambe) abietum* Kiesenwetter, 1859** (Fig. 1)

DATA: Bosnia and Herzegovina: Republika Srpska: Prijedor Municipality: Donja Ljubija: N of Dzamišće Cemetery, 44°56'10.6"N, 16°37'01.2"E, ca. 200 m a.s.l., 18.10.2000, 1 ♂, leg. J. Větřovec, det. I. Plonski, coll. Jar. Větřovec. – The specimen is labelled with "Bosnia-Herzegovina \ Donja Ljubija \ 44.936270°N, 16.617007°E \ 18.10.2000, Větřovec J. lgt."

Figure 1. *Aplocnemus (Diplambe) abietum*, habitus (left) and median lobe (right).

Aplocnemus (Diplambe) abietum is the only known representative of this large and widely dispersed subgenus in the Balkans and is abundant and distributed widely across the entire southern region of the peninsula (Liberti, 2019: 13). Liberti (op. cit.) reports it from Romania (viz. Băile Herculane), North Macedonia (viz. Struga), Bulgaria (viz. Katunsi, Mikrevo, and Petrich), and Greece (numerous localities). The specimen reported above represents the first country record for Bosnia and Herzegovina to date. Furthermore, it is the first specimen found in autumn (G. Liberti in lit., email from 18.02.2024).

Acknowledgments: I thank Jaroslav Větrovec (Hradec Králové, Czechia) for providing me with his material for identification and study. Furthermore, I am grateful to Alice Laciny (Vienna, Austria) and an anonymous reviewer for the linguistic revision of the manuscript. I extend my appreciation to Gianfranco Liberti (Uboldo, Italy), the leading authority on *Diplambe* taxonomy, for reviewing the final manuscript version.

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ПРВИ НАЛАЗ *APLOCNEMUS (DIPLAMBE) ABIETUM* KIESENWETTER, 1859 (COLEOPTERA: RHADALIDAE) У БОСНИ И ХЕРЦЕГОВИНИ

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Извод

Једна јединка *Aplocnemus (Diplambe) abietum* Kiesenwetter, 1859 (Coleoptera: Rhadalidae: Rhadalinae: Aplocnemini) са територије Босне и Херцеговине је регистрована и илустрована.

Received: February 22nd, 2024

Accepted: March 14th, 2024